

**Coherent & Cross-compliant Ocean Governance
for Delivering the EU Green Deal for European Sea**

French Mediterranean case study

Balancing offshore wind energy ambitions and marine biodiversity protection

Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement Grant agreement ID 101060958. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

A French Mediterranean case study on offshore wind energy

Offshore wind energy development is an emerging focus in France, driven by the need to align with European Union objectives for carbon neutrality by 2050, the Renewable Energy Directives (RED I, II, III), and the European Green Deal (EGD). With the second-highest offshore wind potential in Europe (mostly located in the North Sea Channel and Atlantic coastlines), following the United Kingdom, France has introduced an extensive framework of new regulations, strategic plans, and funding mechanisms. These efforts aim to establish at least 50 offshore wind farms by 2050 (45GigaWatts (GW)).

Crossgov research project focuses on how coherence and cross-compliance of marine related policies and legislation affect the ability to realise the EU Green Deal's goals for the protection of marine ecosystems and biodiversity, zero pollution and nature-based climate adaptation and mitigation. In the frame of this project, a case study on France and more specifically the French Provence-Alpes-Côte-D'Azur has been running for 24 months. A part of this case study aims at assessing whether the governance, impact assessments, and funding structures associated with the 2017–2024 offshore wind strategy align with the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), Water Framework Directive (WFD), Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD), and the EGD requirements. The geographic focus has been purposely selected to cover a region which does not have favourable conditions to implement offshore wind farms (physical constraints with a soft soil), using concrete examples to evaluate the feasibility and regulatory compliance of these initiatives.

Assessing French offshore wind energy ambitions and marine biodiversity protection

'Offshore wind power will generate 'thousands of jobs' during construction and bring in €2.5 billion in revenue 'between 2023 and 2035', which will help 'fund our priorities'. 'One third will go to the fishing industry, and so I say this for our fishermen: offshore wind power will enable us to finance €700 million for the fishing industry'
Speech of Emmanuel Macron, President of France, at the "Assises de la mer" conference in Nantes on 28 November 2023.

Historically, in France, marine spatial planning public discussions have been polarised around two issues: fishing and more recently offshore wind energy. These activities respectively reflect the issues of climate and biodiversity crises in the marine context and also symbolise the balance of power between historical and new marine uses (Guyot-Téphany et al., 2024). More recently, offshore wind energy has become a central topic on the French marine-related policy stage. France now ranks 9th in the world with 482 MW installed and its first commercial offshore wind farm was commissioned in 2022 (Trouillet, 2024) and aims to implement an ambitious plan to build around 50 offshore wind farms by 2050 (only four of them would be implemented in the French Mediterranean sea, the others would be in the North Sea Channel and Atlantic Seas), providing a total electricity output of 45 GW (Wolff et al., 2024).

Offshore wind energy development: an interwoven regulation between national energy plans and maritime planning

The planning of offshore marine renewable energies involves a series of interlinked and interlocking laws and texts on energy development and marine planification and biodiversity protection (Figure 1). Procedures were already qualified as “complex” in 2011 (Roche, 2011) even before the MSPD (2014). Indeed, in 2009, the Grenelle 1 and 2 laws setting energy management schemes and objectives for 2020 was considered “far from simplifying applicable rules, it seems on the contrary to make procedures more complex by adding plans and guidelines one on top of the other” (Roche, 2011). Between 2015 and 2023, the energy legislative framework has been enhanced by 3 complementary laws: (a) the law on energy transition for green growth¹ (2015) encouraging the offshore wind sector development, (b) the law on energy and climate² (2019) aiming at lowering at 50% the part of nuclear energy in the energy mix and considering offshore wind energy as an alternative and finally, (c) the law on renewable energy acceleration³ (2023) simplifying administrative procedure for offshore wind projects and underlying the preference for projects located in EEZs as well as introducing the obligation to carry local public debates. The operational planning of marine renewable energies was enforced through two documents: (a) the French Marine strategie (MaS) called Document Stratégique de Façade (2018-2024) delimiting the zones where offshore wind farms could be implemented and (b) the Multiannual energy programming establishing the production targets to reach.

On top of that, three planning documents manage the marine environment (figure 2). The SRADDET⁴, a land-planning document managing activities at sea close to the coast (<300m), the RBMP mostly

Figure 1 marine and energy legislation impacting offshore wind planning in France, source CrossGov French Mediterranean case study

involved with chemical state of the ocean and coastal restoration activities (1nm) and the Document Stratégique de Façade both translating the MSFD and MSPD into concrete actions for biodiversity protection and the uses at sea. Offshore wind development must comply with these three planning documents and more specifically their biodiversity protection objectives.

Figure 2 maritime spatial planning documents involved in offshore wind farms development, source CrossGov French Mediterranean case study

One multi-faceted document for planning biodiversity protection, activities at sea and offshore wind energy

In France, the MSFD and MSPD (including offshore wind) are implemented through a single integrated strategic framework: the Façade Strategic Document (Document Stratégique de Façade, DSF). Four DSF cover the coast and seas of metropolitan France. The DSFs are documents that describe sea and coastal policy orientations and actions in a systematic and prescriptive manner for each façade and include two parts: a strategic and environmental assessment and a plan of actions. It includes a key annex featuring “vocational maps.” These maps outline (among other sectoral activities) designated areas for offshore wind energy development, providing spatial guidance for future projects. The second iteration of the DSF for the Mediterranean façade (2017–2024), analysed for CrossGov, included limited content specifically addressing offshore wind energy.

This DSF is also the strategic environmental assessment (SEA) for a given maritime façade⁵. However, given the fast acceleration of offshore wind energy development, the DSF drafted in 2017 has shown limitation as at the time of its adoption, the French Energy Plan Decree was still in preparation, resulting in the targets not being specified in the strategic objectives. Given that the regulatory obligations for strategic environmental assessment are described in the DSF, they did not incorporate the zoning required to meet the objectives of the French Energy Plan relating to marine renewable energy with sufficient detail. SEAs have therefore been unable to take into account Offshore Wind Energy development from the French Energy planning impacts, nor the cumulative impacts with

those of other activities.⁶

Figure 3 The Document Stratégique de Façade and offshore wind energy, source CrossGov French Mediterranean case study

From a peripheral issue in 2018 to the heart of the 2024 debate

The 2021 Program of Measures (PoMs) within the DSF outlines 17 thematic areas, comprising a total of 92 actions, with only four directly related to offshore wind energy which shows that there was very little consideration of offshore wind energy issued in the 0-12 nautical miles zone. The four actions are (a) Set up a national coordinating body for the coastal scientific councils on offshore wind energy; (b) Capitalise on and disseminate knowledge relating to offshore floating wind turbines and their impact on the environment by ensuring that the various projects are monitored in a harmonised way; (c) Develop a competitive, sustainable, and structured ‘commercial floating wind turbine’ industry on a Mediterranean scale. The last action is (d) “improving understanding and consideration of the cumulative effects of human activities (including offshore wind farms) and ecological carrying capacity”. This low proportion of actions oriented to offshore wind energy draws two distinct conclusions including that until recently offshore wind energy was not considered as the main alternative to nuclear energy, and that the development of offshore wind power is not seen as linked to marine environment management policies but to energy development policies.

In 2024, the integration of offshore wind power is at the forefront of the challenges covered by the French marine environment planning document. Launched in 2024, the public debate for the renewal of the DSF was half focused on biodiversity issues and activities at sea, and the other half exclusively covering offshore wind issues. A lexicometric analysis of the contributions during public debate highlighted that the word “wind” was mentioned more often than the word “environment” underlining the prime importance given to offshore wind energy in the sea-related priorities (Guyot-Téphany et al., 2024).

In this analysis, the environment-related lexicon, however, was considered as “fairly disparate” (Guyot-Téphany et al., 2024, p7), revealing the cross-sectional nature of this topic. This shows a paradigm shift and a change in priorities compared to 2018.

Based on this public debate and on national priorities, the presentation of the main priorities for the marine spatial planning ⁷ (Ministry of ecological transition, 2024) confirms this shift. Carbon neutrality is set as an equal objective to biodiversity protection but is presented on top of the two objectives. Priorities are set in the following order: “the energy transition, the development of our maritime economy, the preservation of the marine environment and the fair treatment of stakeholders”. (a) planification of offshore wind (b) reconcile offshore wind with fisheries and other activities (c) a case-by-case approach to biodiversity protection zones taking into account that, despite the objective to reduce damage to biodiversity through the key role of MPA, the possibility to build an offshore wind farm in an MPA is explicitly mentioned.

Developping offshore wind energy with enhanced scientific knowledge

The scientific knowledge on the maritime public domain (12-24nm) is not exhaustive. A strong stake of the offshore wind energy development is the scientific research. In 2022, the Offshore Wind Observatory was created, as part of the objectives and measures set out in the 2017 National Sea and Coastal Strategy (MSFD). The first calls for research projects launched in 2022, by the Offshore Renewable Energies Observatory, concerned the enhancement of existing knowledge and the acquisition of new knowledge. With a total budget of €20 million, 13 studies were carried out to acquire new knowledge about the marine environment and the impact of wind farms on this environment, as well as four studies to summarise and build on existing knowledge. These studies have been identified on the basis of feedback from the Scientific Councils and the Maritime Councils of the coastal areas (the Mediterranean Council in the Provence-Alpes-Côte-D’azur case study) consulted in 2021. These biodiversity studies were grouped under four themes: the nature of the seabed, different groups of species in terms of their presence, their activities according to the seasons, and their life cycle (reproduction, feeding, resting, migration, wintering), as well as potential interactions (such as noise pollution) with offshore wind turbines. In the Mediterranean sea, three projects have been supported: CAPDONA to assess the ecological status of loose substrates in the Gulf of Lion, FAMOSA to map the seabed in the Gulf of Lion, dBlion to assess and map ambient noise and its impact on marine mammals in the Gulf of Lion. None of the three research projects are located in the PACA region despite one project being on the table since 2017 (Fos-sur-Mer). These researches supported by public fundings can be completed through the offshore wind projects environmental impact assessment (more details below).

Fragile consideration of environmental issues in regulatory authorisations

From a governance standpoint, the regulation and planning of offshore wind energy in France are centralised at the national level, under the supervision of the Ministry of the Ecological Transition and Solidarity.

The construction of an offshore wind farm and its connection facilities requires administrative authorisations to be obtained by the successful bidder for the offshore wind farm, and by RTE (national company of electricity) for the connection, including the offshore substation. The nature of the authorisations⁸ required for the offshore wind farm depends on two possibilities: if the maritime area in which the project is located, either in the public maritime domain or in the EEZ. In the first

scenario, on the public maritime domain, the offshore wind farm developer and RTE must each obtain an environmental authorisation and a concession for use of the public maritime domain by the Departmental Prefect. In the EEZ, the developer and RTE each have a single authorisation that takes the place of all the required authorisations (RED III accelerated procedure). The authorisation is issued by the Maritime Prefect⁹.

Figure 4 Institutions responsible for granted offshore wind farms authorisations, source CrossGov French Mediterranean case study

Authorisation will only be granted by the competent authority after consideration of the impact study, the opinion of the competent State administrative authority for environmental matters and the results of the public consultation carried out. This decision will then specify the conditions accompanying the authorisation as well as ‘the measures intended to avoid, reduce and, where possible, offset the negative effects of the project on the environment’.

The thorny question of tax collection

The expansion of offshore wind energy has led to a reflection for the funding for enhancing biodiversity support measures and researching the environmental impacts of such developments.

Starting in 2024, a green tax, referred to as the Green Fund for Offshore Wind Energy, will be introduced. Tax is imposed on operators on the sale of electricity produced by offshore wind farms. This tax is expected to generate several million euros annually and will be collected by the Water Agencies, which are traditionally tasked with implementing the WFD, and at a lesser extend MSFD. The tax will provide a scientific research fund for each maritime region. Fundings will not cover (a) mandatory regulatory studies (avoid, reduce, compensation) (b) offshore wind farms mandatory environmental monitoring (c) permanent monitoring programs (WFD, MSFD, Natura 2000), (d) socio-economic studies (e) research on technologies dedicated to reducing the impact of offshore wind farms. Thus, many scientific areas are covered and this fund will come as a complement to already existing scientific researches.

The first taxes were collected by the Water agency Seine-Normandie that cover the North Sea

Channel and a first round of call for project has been launched end of 2024. However, in the Mediterranean Sea, such fund might not exist before a long time given that the first offshore wind farm has not been constructed yet.

Despite most offshore wind farms being situated beyond 12 nautical miles in France, the Water Agencies will manage these funds, necessitating an extension of their geographical jurisdiction. The reason why the Water Agencies and not the Interregional Directorate for Seas manage the fund is that they are one of the two public administrations mandated to manage public funds (along with the French Biodiversity Office). However, this shift may exacerbate existing inconsistencies in the distribution of responsibilities among institutions overseeing marine environment management. Such challenges underscore the need for a more cohesive governance framework to ensure the effective integration of biodiversity considerations within offshore wind energy strategies.

Studying biodiversity protection and offshore wind development balanced on the ground: the Golf-de-Fos environmental impact assessment

From an overall point of view, the Environmental Authority has published a deliberate opinion on the strategic document for the Mediterranean coastline ¹⁰. Without going in the detail of the project, the environmental assessment regrets that the DSF do not address the impact of offshore wind energy development on migratory land birds despite millions of wintering birds passing through the Mediterranean sea each year.

At the project scales, in the PACA region studied in CrossGov, one environmental impact assessment (EIA) has been conducted in 2017 to explore the potential of conducting an offshore wind project in the Golfe de Fos. This assessment provides an evaluation of the project's effects on the physical, natural, and human environments, as well as cultural heritage. It also examines the project's alignment with various strategic planning frameworks, including the program of measures (PoMs) under the MSFD and WFD. This EIA document describes eight avoidance measures and 18 reduction measures for a total of 110,000€.

The environmental impact assessment includes a section on policy coherence, but there is an absence of detailed considerations for how in detail the EIA is coherent with the DSF, RBMP or other documents objectives or measures. The EIA mentions "By its very nature, the [...] project is in line with the objectives of the MSFD" (Environmental Impact Assessment, Pilot project for floating wind turbines off the coast of Golfe-de-Fos, 2017, p.44).

The project is gradually coming on stream and will have a total capacity of 750 MW. Since 2022, meetings with stakeholders and initial technical and environmental studies have helped to clarify the contours of a study area for the electrical connection, which was validated in December 2024. Between 2023 and 2026, further studies will be carried out to obtain the necessary administrative authorisations. Construction work is scheduled to start in 2027.

Conclusion ←

In France, to achieve the objectives of the Green Deal, particularly with regard to the protection of biodiversity, it is essential to pay attention to the pace of development of offshore wind projects. With a lack of data, the authorisation system may risk favouring this sector over biodiversity. Synergies must be found with existing planning tools (MSFD and WFD) to ensure the effectiveness of the authorisation procedure, and there must be continued investment in scientific research into the areas around wind farms to understand the cumulative impacts they add to the environment.

Endnotes

- 1 loi n° 2015-992 du 17 août 2015 relative à la transition énergétique pour la croissance verte
- 2 loi n° 2019-1147 du 8 novembre 2019 relative à l'énergie et au climat
- 3 Loi n° 2023-175 du 10 mars 2023 relative à l'accélération de la production d'énergies renouvelables
- 4 Regional plan for planning, sustainable development and territorial equality
- 5 IUCN French Committee (2023). Planning Offshore Wind Projects: 7 Strategic Recommendations for Incorporating Biodiversity into Environmental Assessment
- 6 IUCN French Committee (2023). Planning Offshore Wind Projects: 7 Strategic Recommendations for Incorporating Biodiversity into Environmental Assessment
- 7 https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/documents/20241018_DP_Eolien%20en%20mer.pdf
- 8 <https://www.eoliennesenmer.fr/generalites-eoliennes-en-mer/cadre-reglementaire#:~:text=L'autorisation%20est%20d%C3%A9livr%C3%A9e%20par,leurs%20incidences%20sur%20le%20milieu.>
- 9 Guide d'évaluation des impacts sur l'environnement des parcs éoliens en mer Édition 2017, Ministère de l'Environnement, de l'énergie et de la Mer
- 10 Avis délibéré n° 2021-17 de l'autorité environnementale sur le parc éolien flottant Provence Grand Large (13)

Schematic diagrams of the different stages in the construction and operation of an offshore wind farm

Figure 5 schematic diagrams of the different stages in the construction and operation of an offshore wind farm

Glossary

Policy coherence refers to how well different policies work together. Coherence can be defined as the extent to which policies reinforce each other by promoting synergies or reducing conflicts between their objectives and measures both in design and implementation.

Cross-compliance refers to the concurrent achievement/realisation of multiple Green Deal policies and their associated goals and targets.

Policy refers to a set of objectives, rules and measures that provide guidance for solving a particular societal issue. In CrossGov, policy encompasses substantive documents such as white papers and strategies as well as specific laws and regulations or directives.

Acronyms

DSF	Document Stratégique de Façade
EEZ	Economic Exclusive Zone
EGD	European Green Deal
EIA	Environmental impact assessment
MaS	Marine Strategie. In CrossGov, it refers to a generic term that encompasses planning documents relating to the MSFD. In France, it is the <i>Document Stratégique de Façade</i> .
MSFD	Marine Framework Strategy Directive
MSPD	Marine Spatial planning
PACA	Provence-Alpes-Côte-d'Azur
PoM	Program of Measures. In the document, it refers to the SDAGE and DSF respective programs of measures
RBMP	River Basin Management plan. In France, it is the schéma directeur d'aménagement et de gestion des eaux (SDAGE)
SEA	Strategic environmental assessment
SRADDET	Regional plan for planning, sustainable development and territorial equality (land planning document)
WFD	Water Framework Directive

The policy synthesis is based on the findings in the [CrossGov project's case study](#) on the french Mediterranean focusing on the marine directives and sectoral policies coherence and their effects on marine biodiversity protection in the Provence-Alpes-Côte-D'azur region.

Reference:

Laura Bastide. **Balancing offshore wind energy ambitions and marine biodiversity protection, an example of marine spatial planning in the Provence-Alpes-Côte-d'Azur region** CrossGov, January 2025.

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